

UDC 338.48–6

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17763742

Anna P. IVANKOVA,

Russian State University of Tourism and Service (Moscow, Russia);

Master's student; e-mail: 143144@mail.ru

SWOT ANALYSIS OF ECOTOURISM DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS IN THE BELOMORSKY DISTRICT

Abstract. *The paper presents a SWOT analysis of the prospects for ecotourism development in the Belomorsky District of the Republic of Karelia. The research is based on a comprehensive assessment of the area's natural, cultural, and infrastructural potential. The region's strengths include unique natural landscapes, a high level of environmental preservation, rich cultural heritage, including the Belomorsk Petroglyphs (a UNESCO site), and opportunities for integrating nature and culture into tourist routes. The analysis identified key weaknesses, including the district's remoteness, underdeveloped tourism infrastructure, a shortage of skilled staff, limited marketing capabilities, and pervasive regional corruption that impedes the efficient use of public funds. Opportunities include the growth of domestic tourism, the development of ecological routes and educational programs, and the engagement of private investors. Among the key threats are environmental risks, unstable funding, and weak investment activity. The paper uses visual analysis tools: a Radar Chart, an Influence Factor Diagram, and also proposes quantitative methods for assessing risks and development priorities. The obtained results can be used in formulating regional tourism strategies and making management decisions in the fields of environmental and tourism policy. This paper aims to assess the potential and establish development priorities for ecotourism in the Belomorsky District of the Republic of Karelia using a SWOT analysis. Methodology includes SWOT analysis with data visualization (Radar Chart) and quantitative risk assessment. Results revealed key factors as strengths (unique nature, cultural heritage), weaknesses (infrastructural limitations, personnel deficit), opportunities (growth of domestic tourism), and threats (environmental risks). It was established that the potential is constrained by structural problems, including corruption. The results are applicable for government bodies in developing tourism development strategies and for investors in assessing project risks.*

Keywords: *ecotourism, SWOT-analysis, Belomorskies Petroglyphs, tourism infrastructure, sustainable development, corruption, regional economy*

Citation: *Ivankova, A.P. (2025). SWOT analysis of ecotourism development prospects in the Belomorsky district. *Sovremennyye problemy servisa i turizma [Service and Tourism: Current Challenges]*, 19 (3), 75–84. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17763742. (In Russ.).*

Article History

Received 10 October 2025

Accepted 25 November 2025

Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the author(s).

© 2025 the Author(s)

This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY-SA 4.0).

To view a copy of this license, visit <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/>

ИВАНЬКОВА Анна Петровна,

Российский государственный университет туризма и сервиса (Москва, РФ);

Магистрант Высшей школы туризма и гостеприимства;

e-mail: 143144@mail.ru

SWOT-АНАЛИЗ ПЕРСПЕКТИВ РАЗВИТИЯ ЭКОТУРИЗМА В БЕЛОМОРСКОМ РАЙОНЕ

В статье представлен SWOT-анализ перспектив развития экотуризма в Беломорском районе Республики Карелия. Исследование основано на комплексной оценке природного, культурного и инфраструктурного потенциала территории. К числу сильных сторон региона отнесены уникальные природные ландшафты, высокий уровень экологической сохранности, богатое культурное наследие, включая Беломорские петроглифы (ЮНЕСКО), а также возможности для интеграции природы и культуры в туристические маршруты. Выделены основные слабые стороны, такие как удаленность района, низкий уровень развития туристической инфраструктуры, дефицит квалифицированных кадров, ограниченные рекламные ресурсы и высокий уровень региональной коррупции, затрудняющий эффективное освоение бюджетных средств. В числе возможностей рассматриваются рост внутреннего туризма, развитие экологических маршрутов, образовательных программ и вовлечение частных инвесторов. Среди ключевых угроз – экологические риски, нестабильность финансирования и слабая инвестиционная активность. В статье использованы визуальные инструменты анализа: диаграмма «Паутинка», диаграмма влияния факторов, а также предложены количественные методы для оценки рисков и приоритетов развития. Полученные результаты могут быть использованы при формировании стратегий регионального туризма и принятии управленческих решений в сфере природоохранной и туристической политики.

Цель статьи – определение потенциала и приоритетных направлений развития экотуризма в Беломорском районе Республики Карелия на основе проведения SWOT-анализа.

Метод или методология проведения работы: в статье использовались метод SWOT-анализа для структурированной оценки внутренних (сильные и слабые стороны) и внешних (возможности и угрозы) факторов, а также визуализация данных с помощью диаграммы «Паутинка» (Radar Chart), диаграмма влияния факторов, а также предложены количественные методы для оценки рисков и приоритетов развития.

Результаты: Выявлены ключевые сильные стороны (уникальная природа, богатое культурное наследие), слабые стороны (удаленность, слабая инфраструктура, нехватка кадров, коррупция), возможности (развитие экологических маршрутов, рост внутреннего туризма, привлечение инвестиций) и угрозы (риск экологических нарушений, ограниченные финансовые ресурсы) для развития экотуризма в регионе. Установлено, что существующий потенциал сдер-

живается структурными проблемами, в особенности коррупцией и низким качеством управления проектами.

Область применения результатов: полученные результаты целесообразно применять в деятельности органов государственной и региональной власти для формирования стратегий развития туризма, а также для потенциальных инвесторов и предпринимателей при оценке рисков и возможностей реализации проектов в сфере экотуризма в Беломорском районе.

Ключевые слова: экотуризм, SWOT-анализ, Беломорские петроглифы, туристическая инфраструктура, устойчивое развитие, коррупция, экономика региона

Для цитирования: Иванькова, А.П. SWOT-анализ перспектив развития экотуризма в Беломорском районе / А. П. Иванькова. *Современные проблемы сервиса и туризма*. 2025. Т. 19. № 3. С. 75–84. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17763742.

Дата поступления в редакцию: 10 октября 2025 г.

Дата утверждения в печать: 25 ноября 2025 г.

Introduction

SWOT analysis (from English Strengths – strengths, Weaknesses – weaknesses, Opportunities – opportunities, Threats – threats) is a strategic planning method aimed at identifying and assessing internal and external factors influencing the development of the research object. This methodology was first proposed in the 1960s by the American researcher Albert S. Humphrey as part of a Stanford University project dedicated to improving corporate management and long-term planning. SWOT analysis is based on a structured approach to assessing four key components: internal strengths and weaknesses, as well as external opportunities and threats, and is applied for developing strategies in various sectors of the economy and for economic development [9; 12].

The development of ecotourism in the Belomorsky District is supported by a solid legislative framework that guarantees the preservation of the natural environment during recreational use, in accordance with the principles established in the Federal Law “On Environmental Protection” [1]. The region possesses significant potential for tourism development, recognized at the federal level within the Tourism Development Strategy in the Russian Federation until 2035 [5] and supported by republican legislation [2]. The implementation of tourism projects in the Belomorsky District is carried out within the framework of long-term program documents, including the state program of Karelia “Tourism Development” [4] and the Federal Targeted Program for the Development of the Republic and national project until 2030 [6], ensuring systematic support for initiatives.

Strengths: unique nature, rich cultural heritage

1. Unique nature

The Belomorsky District of Karelia possesses significant advantages for the development of ecotourism, the main ones being its unique nature and rich cultural heritage. The district is located on the coast of the White Sea – one of the most beautiful and ecologically clean seas in Russia, with rich marine biodiversity and picturesque beaches, creating excellent conditions for water-based and

pedestrian eco-tours. The water resources of the Belomorsky District, including the Vyg River and its tributaries, create excellent conditions for organizing active recreation. The clean waters and scenic shorelines are ideal for kayaking and canoeing, as well as for fishing. The natural landscapes of the region are characterized by significant diversity – from coniferous forests to tundra zones. This provides ample opportunities for hiking and observing local flora and fauna. The good preservation of natural ecosystems is of particular value, attracting lovers of pristine nature.

The cultural heritage of the district is represented by unique archaeological sites, among which the Belomorsk Petroglyphs stand out. These ancient images complement the natural attractions and enrich educational routes. The preservation of the traditional way of life of the local population allows for the development of ethnographic tourism, introducing visitors to the cultural characteristics and crafts of the region.

All these factors create the potential for the formation of a sustainable ecotourism cluster with minimal impact on the environment, considering the national project “Environmental Well-being,” according to Decree No. 309 of May 7, 2024, “On the National Development Goals of the Russian Federation for the Period until 2030,” and open up opportunities for the development of environmental education and scientific tourism [3]. Thus, the unique natural and cultural resources of the Belomorsky District form a solid foundation for the successful and sustainable development of ecotourism in the region.

2. Rich Cultural Heritage.

The Belomorsky District of Karelia possesses a unique cultural heritage, which serves as an important resource for the development of ecotourism. The Belomorsk Petroglyphs hold particular significance – ancient rock carvings recognized as a UNESCO World Heritage Site, attracting numerous researchers and travelers. The district is home to preserved old Pomor villages, including Sumsky Posad, Virma, Sukhoye, Kolezhma, and Nyukhcha, where visitors can learn about the traditional way of life, local crafts, and features of Pomor cuisine. Monuments of wooden

architecture, showcasing the distinctive style of Pomor architecture, are also of great value. An additional incentive for tourism development comes from regularly held ecological and cultural festivals, which not only attract visitors to the region but also contribute to the preservation of local traditions among the population.

3. Integration of Nature and Culture in Ecotourism Routes.

The Belomorsky District offers unique opportunities for creating comprehensive ecotourism routes that organically combine natural attractions and cultural sites. Tourists have the opportunity to simultaneously explore the region's natural wealth – the waters of the White Sea, river systems, forest areas, and the famous petroglyphs – while also visiting historical pomor villages and architectural monuments. This integrated approach helps travelers form a holistic perception of the territory, deeply revealing the interconnections between the natural environment and pomor cultural traditions. The educational components of the routes are particularly important, aimed at enhancing the environmental awareness of tourists and fostering a responsible attitude towards preserving both the natural and cultural heritage of the region [11].

Thus, the natural and cultural resources of the Belomorsky District form a solid foundation for the sustainable development of ecotourism and the creation of attractive tourism products. Figure 1 presents a Radar Chart: Strengths in the Belomorsky District. Each of the key characteristics (unique nature, cultural heritage, ecological purity, etc.) is assigned a score on a 10-point scale, reflecting its significance and level of development. The chart helps to visually assess the balance of potential and identify priority areas for support and development.

Weaknesses: remoteness, weak infrastructure, corruption

1. Remoteness of the region from Petrozavodsk.

Despite significant natural and cultural resources, the Belomorsky District faces a number of weaknesses that complicate the development of ecotourism. The main problem is the region's remoteness from major transport

hubs and tourist centers. The nearest airports are in Petrozavodsk ("Besovets") and Murmansk ("Murmashi"), located approximately 280 km south and 350 km north of Belomorsk, respectively. Regular flights connect both airports with Moscow, St. Petersburg, and other Russian regions. The number of bus and railway routes is also limited. Belomorsk in Karelia is accessible by rail from Moscow, St. Petersburg, Murmansk, and Vologda. Direct trains run primarily from the capital cities, with infrequent schedules that only increase during the summer. For example, train #381 Moscow-Belomorsk runs twice a week, while #655 St. Petersburg-Belomorsk runs daily in summer and less frequently in winter. An alternative – traveling to Kandalaksha or Kem with a subsequent transfer – also reduces the district's accessibility for tourists. The internal transport infrastructure is also underdeveloped: poor road quality hinders travel along ecotourism routes, especially in remote areas.

Fig. 1. Radar Chart: Strengths of Ecotourism in the Belomorsky District [compiled by the author]

2. Weak tourism infrastructure.

The Belomorsky District experiences problems with tourism infrastructure, which limits the development of ecotourism. The main difficulty is the lack of quality accommodation, especially in remote locations, where hotels, guest houses, and eco-lodges often do not meet modern standards [7]. In the Belomorsky District, tourists can stay in several small guest houses like "Ethnopark Lopsky Bereg," "Barskie Khoromy," "Otdykh u Reki," and the eco-lodge "Vygostrov," with a total room stock of 41 rooms. The district

also has several small hotels: Chaika 2*, Gandvik 3*, and Starchina, collectively offering 47 rooms. Many villages lack convenient accommodation facilities, reducing comfort for tourists. Furthermore, there is a lack of necessary infrastructure for active recreation: safe and equipped routes with navigation, parking, toilets, and rest areas are not yet developed. A shortage of service points – cafes, bakeries, vending machines, and equipment rental outlets – also affects the level of amenities.

3. Shortage of Qualified Personnel.

A significant problem for the development of ecotourism in the Belomorsky District is the shortage of qualified personnel, which negatively impacts the quality of tourist services. The region acutely lacks professional, accredited guides due to the absence of specialized educational programs, training courses, and a lack of desire among local residents for development and education. Although local residents possess knowledge about the area's nature and culture, they often lack the necessary skills for psychological interaction with tourists to conduct professionally high-quality excursions. Officially, guided tours of the petroglyphs are conducted by the State Autonomous Institution of the Republic of Karelia "Center for the Management of Karelia's Petroglyphs" [15]. Most offers on the market are provided by private guides working unofficially. They promote their services through one-page websites and the social network "VKontakte." The number of certified tours is insufficient, and the quality of services, including the guides' appearance, often fails to meet professional standards. To improve the situation, it is necessary to develop educational programs, enhance the qualifications of specialists, and improve foreign language skills for working with international guests (tourists).

4. Limited Promotional and Information Resources.

Limited promotional and information resources represent another weakness of the Belomorsky District in developing ecotourism. The region lacks a developed marketing strategy, leading to low visibility in the tourism

market. The absence of quality advertising and poor awareness among potential tourists hinder the region's promotion compared to more popular destinations. Furthermore, the information support infrastructure is underdeveloped – there are no modern websites, mobile applications, or tourist information centers (TICs). These factors, combined with the district's remoteness, limited infrastructure, seasonality of tourist flow, and shortage of qualified personnel, create significant obstacles to the development of ecotourism. Nevertheless, coordinated efforts at the state and regional policy levels, along with investments in infrastructure and marketing, could significantly improve the situation and ensure the sustainable development of the tourism industry.

5. High Level of Corruption and Insufficient Transparency in Project Implementation.

A significant problem hindering the development of ecotourism and infrastructure in the Belomorsky District is the high level of corruption at the regional level. Despite substantial budgetary funds allocated for the development of tourism project facilities, the effectiveness of their use raises legitimate doubts. An example is the construction of the "Belomorsk Petroglyphs" Visitor Center – a large-scale facility with a 40-room hotel, a restaurant, a museum exhibition, and a conference hall. A contract with the Karelian company "Development Group LLC" was signed in March 2023 with a planned completion date of December 2024, but the facility was only delivered in the spring of 2025. The total project cost amounted to 440 million rubles [14]. Furthermore, the quality of construction and materials used is significantly inferior to market standards and the overall scale expected for a project of such a budget, raising questions about the expediency and transparency of the expenditures.

The project implementation process has been marked by such negative practices as the participation of shell companies affiliated with the projects, created specifically to secure contracts, coupled with the absence of an effective system for monitoring the use of budgetary funds. These companies lack a sustainable business reputation and professional

competencies. This leads to risks of falsified reporting and misappropriation of resources, which significantly hinders the development of tourism infrastructure and reduces investor and tourist confidence in the region.

Thus, corruption risks and weak control over budgetary expenditures remain serious obstacles to the sustainable development of ecotourism in the Belomorsky District.

Opportunities: Development of Ecological Routes, Growth of Domestic Tourism

The development of ecotourism in the Belomorsky District possesses significant opportunities, which can be divided into several key areas:

1. Development of Ecological Routes.

The development of ecotourism in the Belomorsky District opens significant opportunities for enhancing the region's tourist appeal and stimulating its economic growth. Primarily, this is associated with the creation and development of ecological routes that can attract tourists interested in active recreation and exploring nature and culture. The natural resources of the Belomorsky District – forests, water bodies, and the sea coast – create a favorable environment for active tourism. Iconic attractions like the petroglyphs and the Vyg River can become nodal elements of tourist routes. Educational programs revealing the ecological and historical-cultural aspects of the territory will enrich travels with meaningful content. The formation of an interconnected network of routes with the necessary infrastructure will provide guests with diverse experiences and extend their length of stay in the region.

The implementation of these measures will contribute to attracting both domestic and foreign tourists, laying the foundations for the balanced development of the ecotourism industry in the Belomorsky region.

2. Growth of Domestic Tourism.

The growing interest in domestic tourism opens up new opportunities for the development of ecological recreation in the Belomorsky District. In the context of a changing economic situation, many Russian travelers are opting for safe and eco-friendly vacations within the country. This district attracts

tourists with its pristine nature and cultural heritage, offering an alternative to popular resorts. Active types of recreation are particularly popular – hiking, river rafting, fishing, and wildlife observation. These areas are successfully developing in the region with minimal intervention in the ecosystem. An additional advantage is the cultural and historical monuments, including the UNESCO-protected Belomorsk Petroglyphs and authentic Pomor settlements. State programs supporting domestic tourism contribute to the development of necessary infrastructure and increasing the region's visibility. These measures help increase tourist flow and create conditions for the sustainable development of ecotourism in the Belomorsky District.

3. Investments and Private Entrepreneurship.

The development of ecotourism in the Belomorsky District presents significant opportunities for attracting both public and private investments. The creation of necessary tourist infrastructure – accommodation facilities (tourist bases, hostels, hotels), educational centers, and tourist sites – requires substantial financial investments, which can be secured through sustainable tourism support programs and interested investors. Furthermore, the development of ecotourism stimulates local entrepreneurship, supporting small and medium-sized businesses related to the tourism sector: crafts, souvenir production, transport services, cafes, and mini-stores [13]. Thanks to the expansion of ecological routes, the growth of domestic tourism, and the application of foreign experience from leading countries in the field of ecotourism [8;10], the Belomorsky District has good prospects for sustainable tourism development, job creation, and infrastructure improvement, which will ultimately enhance the region's attractiveness for tourists and strengthen its economic potential.

Threats: Risk of Environmental Violations, Limited Financial Resources

1. Risk of Environmental Violations.

The development of ecotourism in the Belomorsky District faces a complex of environmental challenges requiring a balanced approach. The primary concern is the

recreational load on natural ecosystems – intensive visits to popular locations can lead to the degradation of forest areas, water sources, and animal habitats. The lack of developed waste disposal infrastructure creates risks of territory pollution, which contradicts the concept of eco-friendly recreation. Iconic sites, including the water area of the Vyg River and the territories where the Belomorsk Petroglyphs are located, demonstrate particular vulnerability. Their preservation requires thoughtful zoning and regulation of tourist flow. An additional factor of uncertainty is climate change, which can affect the accessibility of certain routes. Minimizing these risks is possible through the implementation of a system for monitoring the ecological capacity of territories and the development of adaptive management decisions.

2. Limited Financial Resources.

The development of ecotourism in the Belomorsky District is hampered by a lack of funding necessary for implementing large-scale projects. The main problems are associated with insufficient funds for creating and maintaining infrastructure – constructing accommodation facilities (tourist bases, hostels, hotels), rest areas,

improving navigation, and other facilities. Limited budgetary capabilities and a shortage of private investors slow down the region's development as a tourist destination. Furthermore, the lack of finances hinders the implementation of effective marketing campaigns needed to promote ecotourism in domestic and international markets. A significant reliance on state subsidies and grants makes projects vulnerable to changes in funding policies. Concurrently, economic instability reduces the interest of private investors, who consider investments in ecotourism too risky. Without active business support and expanded investment, the development of ecotourism in the district may slow down. Figure 2 presents a diagram of the influence of SWOT analysis factors on the development of ecotourism in the Belomorsky District.

Decoding:

Strengths (Green): Play a key role, especially “Unique Nature” (score 9) and “Cultural Heritage” (8).

Weaknesses (Red): “Corruption and Inefficiency” (8) and “Limited Financial Resources” (7) can significantly hinder development.

Fig. 2. Influence of SWOT Analysis Factors on Ecotourism Development in the Belomorsky District [compiled by the author]

Opportunities (Blue): “Growth of Domestic Tourism” (7) and “Environmental Education” (6) have high potential.

Threats (Orange): “Low Investor Interest” and “Dependence on State Support” (5–6) are moderate barriers.

The radar chart visually illustrates the priorities and vulnerabilities for the strategic planning of ecotourism development.

Quantitative Methods for Assessing Risks and Development Priorities of Ecotourism in the Belomorsky District Based on SWOT Analysis

A priority and risk scale from 1 to 5 is used, where:

- 1 – Minimal influence/risk;
- 5 – Maximum influence/risk.

A weight coefficient for each factor is additionally calculated as follows:

Priority Score × Risk Score = Final Impact Score (for prioritization)

Conclusion

The SWOT analysis demonstrated that the Belomorsky District possesses significant potential for ecotourism

development due to its unique natural resources, cultural heritage, growing domestic tourism interest, and opportunities for attracting investment. However, this potential is constrained by a number of serious weaknesses and threats. The main problems include weak infrastructure, a shortage of qualified personnel, insufficient promotional activities, and a high level of corruption. The latter factor has a particularly acute impact on project implementation efficiency: despite substantial budget allocations, quality outcomes are often lacking, and control over expenditure remains formal.

Successful development of ecotourism in the region is only possible under the condition of systematic work: ensuring transparency in budgetary processes, supporting local businesses, training specialists, and implementing sustainable tourism standards. Without addressing the current weaknesses and minimizing threats, the tourism potential of the Belomorsky District may remain unrealized.

Table 1. Quantitative Methods for Assessing Risks and Development Priorities of Ecotourism in the Belomorsky District Based on SWOT Analysis [compiled by the author]

No.	Factor (by SWOT)	Type	Priority (1–5)	Risk (1–5)	Total Score (Priority × Risk)
1	Unique Nature and Biodiversity	Strength	5	1	5
2	Belomorsk Petroglyphs (UNESCO)	Strength	5	1	5
3	Preserved Pomor Villages and Traditions	Strength	4	2	8
4	Opportunity for Nature-Culture Integration	Opportunity	5	2	10
5	High Level of Corruption and Inefficient Spending	Weakness	5	5	25
6	Lack of Budget Control System	Weakness	4	5	20
7	Creation of Shell Companies for State Contracts	Threat	4	5	20
8	Risks of Falsified Reporting	Threat	3	5	15
9	Growth of Tourist Flow and Infrastructure Development	Opportunity	4	2	8
10	Transition to Sustainable and Educational Tourism	Opportunity	5	1	5

References

1. “Ob okhrane okruzhayushchei sredy” [“On Environmental Protection”]: Federal Law No. 7-FZ dated on January 10, 2002 (as amended on August 8, 2024). URL: https://www.consultant.ru/document/cons_doc_LAW_34823/. (Accessed on July 30, 2025). (In Russ.).
2. “O nekotorykh voprosakh razvitiya turizma i turistskoi deyatel’nosti v Respublike Kareliya” [“On Certain Issues of Tourism Development and Tourist Activities in the Republic of Karelia”]: Law of the Republic of Karelia No. 2117-ZRK dated on May 2, 2017 (as amended by No. 2985-ZRK on September 24, 2024, by No. 3022-ZRK on December 16, 2024). (Accessed on August 07, 2025). (In Russ.).
3. “O natsional’nykh tselyakh razvitiya Rossiiskoi Federatsii na period do 2030 goda i na perspektivu do 2036 goda” [“On the National Development Goals of the Russian Federation for the Period until 2030 and for the Future until 2036”]: Decree of the President of the Russian Federation dated on May 7, 2024, No. 309. (n.d.). National Project “Environmental Well-being”. URL: https://www.mnr.gov.ru/activity/np_ecology/. (Accessed on July 30, 2025). (In Russ.).
4. “Ob utverzhdenii Gosudarstvennoi programmy Respubliki Kareliya “Razvitie turizma”” [“On the Approval of the State Program of the Republic of Karelia ‘Tourism Development’”]: Decree of the Government of the Republic of Karelia No. 11-P dated on January 28, 2016 (as amended by No. 399-P on December 3, 2024). (Accessed on August 14, 2025). (In Russ.).
5. *Strategiia razvitiia turizma v Rossiiskoi Federatsii na period do 2035 goda [Tourism Development Strategy in the Russian Federation for the period up to 2035]*: Approved by Order of the Government of the Russian Federation No. 2129-r dated on September 20, 2019. (as amended on November 23, 2020). URL: <https://www.garant.ru>. (Accessed on August 14, 2025). (In Russ.).
6. “Razvitie Respubliki Kareliya do 2030 goda” [“Development of the Republic of Karelia until 2030”]: Federal Targeted Program approved by the Decree of the Government of the Russian Federation on June 9, 2015, No. 570. (In Russ.).
7. *Turisticheskie uslugi. Ekologicheski turizm. Obshchie trebovaniya [Tourism services. Ecological tourism/nature tourism. General requirements]*: State Standard R 56642–2015 dated on 2016. Moscow: Standartinform. (In Russ.).
8. Afanasieva, A. V. (2020). Foreign experience of ecological tourism management: the trends and development models. *Servis v Rossii i za rubezhom [Services in Russia and Abroad]*, 14(3), 27–56. doi: 10.24411/1995-042X-2020-10303. (In Russ.).
9. Vikhanovsky, O. S., & Naumov, A. I. (2009). Management: tutorial (5th ed.). Moscow: “Economist”. (In Russ.).
10. Ilkevich, S. V. (2017). Organizational and economic principles of design, development and improvement of suburban walking trails. *Servis v Rossii i za rubezhom [Services in Russia and Abroad]*, 11(3), 62–76. doi: 10.22412/1995-042X-11-3-6. (In Russ.).
11. Karpova, G. A. (2016). Rol’ ekologizatsii turizma v razvitii regiona [Role of greening of tourism in development of the region]. *Izvestiya Sankt-Peterburgskogo gosudarstvennogo ekonomicheskogo universiteta [Izvestia of Saint Petersburg State University of Economics]*, 2(98), 59–65. (In Russ.).
12. Nosko, P. A. (2019). Analiz natsional’nogo proekta «Ekologiya» posredstvom SWOT-analiza [Analysis of the national project “Ecology” by means of SWOT analysis]. *National Security*, 6, 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.7256/2454-0668.2019.6.31325>. (In Russ.).
13. Abramova, M. I., Aleksushin, G. V., Antyufeeva, T. V., et al. (2022). *Ekologicheskii turizm: sovremennye vektory razvitiya [Ecotourism: Modern Development Vectors]*: monograph. Yekaterinburg: Ural State Pedagogical University. (In Russ.).
14. Dobrodei, I. (2024). Vizit-tsentr na belomorskikh petroglifakh za 440 mln dostroyat osen’yu [Visitor Center at the Belomorsk Petroglyphs to Be Built for 440 Million Rubles]. *RBC news*. URL: <https://karelia.rbc.ru/karelia/30/07/2024/66a8b6ea9a7947d54e0a7c2d> (Accessed on August 20, 2025). (In Russ.).
15. “Tsentр po Upravleniyu Petroglifami Karelii” [State Autonomous Institution of the Republic of Karelia “Center for the Management of Karelia’s Petroglyphs”]. URL: <https://www.rusprofile.ru/id/1231000001924> (Accessed on August 20, 2025). (In Russ.).